

Marketing Mix and Service Quality Dimension as Determinants of Customer Satisfaction on Selected Beach Resorts of IGACOS, Davao Del Norte, Philippines

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Abstract: This study aimed to determine the relationship between the marketing mix, service quality, and customer satisfaction on selected beach resorts in Island Garden City of Samal, Davao del Norte. A descriptive correlational design was used in this study with 300 respondents. To determine the interrelationships between the marketing mix and service quality to customer satisfaction. Pearson product-moment correlation was used in the study. Multiple linear regressions were employed to evaluate the major predictor of customer satisfaction. This analysis revealed that the extent level of the marketing mix as perceived by beach resort guests was high. Still, the level of service quality and customer satisfaction were also very high. Moreover, the marketing mix was moderately significant to customer satisfaction, and service quality was highly correlated to customer satisfaction. On the other hand, the independent variables—marketing mix and service quality could significantly influence customer satisfaction. The researcher recommends the owner should always be on the lookout for new ways to advertise their business.

Keywords: Marketing Mix, Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Beach Resorts, Davao del Norte, Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

Satisfying customers is the primary concern for every resort and hotel (Guray, 2018). Every Beach resort's success is determined by how satisfied their guests are with the quality of the products and service provided by the resort and the first goal must always be the guests, followed by profit (De Guzman, Abanilla, & Abarquez, 2020). Hence, providing and maintaining customer satisfaction is one of the biggest challenges for the managers and business people in any industry (Radojevic, Stanic & Stanic, 2015; Yen-Lun, 2004) because of many factors (Liu, Teichert, Rossi, Li & Hu, 2017). On the other hand, when the guests experienced dissatisfaction with a company's products or services, they are more likely to complain about it (Kim, Kim & Heo, 2019). Unfavorable outcomes arise when clients are unsatisfied. They express their dissatisfaction by spreading negative word-of-mouth, changing service providers, or filing a complaint with the company (Kim, 2015). Hence, satisfaction depends on many factors, internal and external factors (Haarhoff, 2018).

Concurrently, customer satisfaction is essential in the company because it leads to higher customer loyalty, repeat guests (Peppers & Rogers, 2016), and customer retention of the products and services, which results in a positive or increase of profits (Magatef & Tomalieh, 2015). Also, it offers a tool for the company's managers and business owners to improve and develop their marketing & management strategies (Atabeb, 2019). Customers of today are willing to retain in the businesses that exceed and meet the customer requirements and turn customer experience into an unforgettable and excellent experience (Kuo & Chen, 2015).

It is the main reason why managers of resorts focus on improving and creating marketing strategies. To boost a destination's appeal to potential guest as well as positioning the destination in the market and highlighting its competitive advantages (Mendaña & Apritado, 2021). It was added by Kubickova & Martin (2020) that destinations must generate and innovate new products, markets, and customers by thinking more like businesses. Moreover, the tourism industry stays long, successful, and profitable. Somocor (2017) concluded that customer satisfaction has a relationship to the appropriateness of the marketing mix and the quality of services of the business establishment.

The researcher has come across a few studies dealing with marketing mix strategies and customer satisfaction in the hotel industry, but nothing about the beach resorts of the Island Garden City of Samal. Therefore, there still a lack of research in marketing mix strategies, service quality, and customer satisfaction that warrants this investigation. This study may help owners/managers, especially small beach resorts, to market their businesses and resolve the problem of customer dissatisfaction and poor-quality service. Samal is known as one of the tourist spots or visited places of Davao del Norte.

The main objective of this study was to identify the factors that lead to customer satisfaction that include marketing mix strategies and service quality dimensions of the selected beach resorts in Island Garden City of Samal, Davao del Norte. Specifically, determined the extent of implementation of the marketing mix strategies of beach resorts as experienced by the customers; assessed the service quality attributes level of the selected resort as experienced by the customers; determined the level of customer satisfaction of the customers of selected resorts when it comes to purchase retention, repeat purchase and loyalty of the customer; tested the significant relationship between the marketing mix strategies and customer satisfaction, and between service quality attributes and customer satisfaction; tested which between marketing mix strategy and service quality significantly influences customer satisfaction.

II. METHODOLOGY

The researcher used the descriptive-correlational research method. Descriptive research examines a population's characteristics, identifies problems within a group, business, or demographic, or examines differences in traits or practices between organizations or even countries. (Siedlecki, 2020). It investigates and describes the extent to which the link between two or more variables corresponds to the change of variables by describing current actions and processes. (Kowalczyk, 2017).

Correlational research is used to find links or relationships between or among variables, as well as to answer queries based on current occurrences (Dulock, 1993). Ex post facto studies are what they're called when they're done after the fact. The term "design" refers to the fact that the work was completed following the occurrence of a natural phenomenon of interest (Simon, 2011).

This study was conducted in four selected beach resorts in IGACOS Davao del Norte. IGACOS is an island with several commercial resorts and private beaches scattered across the white sand length of 118 kilometers. The record of the City Investment and Tourism Office shows that there are 86 registered beach resorts in the island. The researcher chose these beach resorts in IGACOS, which offers the same products and services like accommodations, foods, and beverages (restaurant) and other amenities (function room, gym, water activities). The resorts are officially registered in the City Investment and Tourism Office. Beach resorts in the Island Garden City of Samal is one of the best areas to conduct the study since it is one of the most visited destinations in Davao del Norte and is considered the country's biggest island. The respondents of this study were the 300 guests/customers from four beach resorts. They were purposively chosen based on these criteria—they must be at least 18 years old and have visited the resort at least twice to prove that they have availed of the products and services offered by the beach resorts.

This study employed an adapted survey questionnaire from Somocor (2017)'s study. The marketing mix strategy has four domains—product, promotion, price, and place. Also, the service quality attributes have five indicators like tangibility, responsiveness, tangibility, assurance and, empathy while repeat purchase, purchase intention, and loyalty for customer satisfaction.

The questionnaire is divided into three sections. The first section is the demographic profile of the respondents, the second section is the marketing mix strategy & service quality, and the last section is customer satisfaction. The research instrument was examined and checked by the panel of examiners prior to its implementation. In the marketing mix section, service quality and customer satisfaction it utilizes a 5-point Likert scale.

The researcher personally asked permission from the beach resorts owner and or manager with the aid of the letter. After the approval of the beach resorts management, the researcher tapped enumerators to do the survey.

The enumerators invited each of the prospective qualified respondents to participate in the study. After the prospective participant agreed, the enumerator asked him/her to read and sign the informed consent form (ICF) as an acknowledgment and agreement that they fully understood the following: the objective of the study, the study procedure or process, the potential discomforts and benefits, the right to privacy and confidentiality, and the right to

withdraw. The enumerators ensured 100 percent retrieval of the questionnaires. The enumerator sent the collected tools to the researcher.

The encoded data were collated, analyzed, and interpreted using different statistical tool such as mean, standard deviation, Pearson r and multiple regression. Mean was used to describe the extent of implementation of the marketing mix, level of quality services, and level of customer satisfaction. Standard Deviation was utilized to measure the amount of variation or dispersion of the responses of the respondents. The significant link between the independent variables, marketing mix strategy, and service quality, and the dependent variable, customer satisfaction, was determined using Pearson r. *Multiple Regression* was done to determine which between the marketing mix strategy, and service quality significantly influences customer satisfaction. Social value, informed consent, vulnerability issues, risk-benefit and safety, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, researcher qualification, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement were among the 10 dimensions of research ethics that the researcher noted.

III. RESULTS

The ratings of the respondents on the level of the marketing mix in terms of product, promotion, place, and price are presented in Table 1. The marketing mix has an overall mean rating of 4.11, which is described as high. It could be noted, however, that the standard deviation (SD) ranges from 0.48 to 1.11. The SDs, which are lower than 1.00, denotes the homogeneity, while those that are greater than 1.00 connotes heterogeneity of the responses of the respondents.

The level of marketing mix in terms of product got a category mean of 4.43 with a very high description. It implies that the marketing mix implementation is very extensive. The highest mean score of 4.47 (very high) was obtained by the item-- *spacious, clean, and well-maintained rooms and cottages*.

As regards to the place, it was rated as very high by the guests with a category mean of 4.35. Of the four items in this domain, the *conduciveness of the beach resorts for stay and relaxation* acquired the highest mean value of 4.53 or described as very high. It explains that the guests agreed that the places are encouraging places for relaxation and stay. On the other hand, the item *accessibility to the police station* got the lowest mean score of 4.07 or has a description of high.

In terms of promotion, it obtained a category mean of 3.57, described as high. This result means that the resort is extensively promoted as experienced by the respondents. The item in this category that received the highest mean score of 4.43 (very high) pertains to the *promotion through social media like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter*. This result connotes that internet-based promotional mechanisms are extensively utilized. On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 3.11 (average) refers to the *promotion through sponsorship or exchange deal*.

The price got an overall category mean of 4.09 or portrayed as high. It means that the price as a marketing mix strategy is extensive. The result shows that the item diversity of package selection yielded the highest mean score of 4.27 (very high). In contrast, the item *reasonability of rates of water activities* was rated by the guests with the lowest with a mean score of 3.87 and a standard deviation of 0.91.

Table 1. Extent of Implementation of Marketing Mix Strategy

Marketing Mix Strategy	Mean	SD	Description
A. Product			
1. availability of varied menu and beverages	4.39	0.66	Very high
2. space, cleanliness and maintenance of rooms and cottages	4.47	0.66	Very high
3. availability of water activities (Banana Boat, Kayak, and the like)	4.44	0.74	Very high
4. offering function rooms for special events.	4.42	0.72	Very high
Category Mean	4.43	0.56	Very high
B. Promotion			
Promotion through			
1. TV Advertisement	3.36	1.06	Average
2. Radio Advertisement	3.31	1.03	Average
3. Press conference	3.27	1.04	Average
4. Brochure/leaflets and banners	3.76	0.98	Average
5. Online advertisement	4.15	0.88	High
6. Social Media (Face book, Instagram, Twitter)	4.43	0.84	Very high

7. Personal Marketing	3.59	1.10	High
8. Direct Mail	3.17	1.11	Average
9. Sponsorship/Exchange deal	3.11	1.08	Average
Category Mean	3.57	0.73	High
C. Place			
1. cleanliness and maintenance	4.45	0.72	Very high
2. conduciveness for stay and relaxation	4.53	0.65	Very high
3. aesthetic value for picture taking	4.50	0.66	Very high
4. accessibility to public transportation	4.22	0.79	Very high
5. accessibility to police station	4.07	0.85	High
Category Mean	4.35	0.58	Very high
D. Price			
1. affordability of products/services rates	4.23	0.82	Very high
2. diversity of package selection	4.27	0.76	Very high
3. reasonability of rates/fees of water activities	3.98	0.83	High
4. provision of students' special rate.	3.87	0.91	High
Category Mean	4.09	0.72	High
Overall Mean	4.11	0.48	High

The data on the beach resort's service quality assessment is presented in Table 2. The overall mean of service quality is 4.44, which is considered excellent. The responses are consistent, with a standard deviation ranging from .55 to .79.

In terms of reliability, the category mean score of 4.35, which is considered very high, indicates that guests consistently enjoy high quality in terms of reliability. The item efficiency of reservation management received significant mean score of 4.38 (very high), while the timeliness of service delivery received the lowest mean score of 4.30 (still extremely high).

The tangibility domain has a category mean of 4.44 or described as very high. The item on the *courteousness of the personnel* got the highest mean score of 4.54 (very high), while the item *accessibility of the location* has the lowest mean score of 4.23, although still described as very high. Responsiveness obtained a category mean of 4.50 or described as very high. The aspect of assurance, on the other hand, yielded a category mean of 4.48 described as very high. The strength of the resort in this area is attributed on the safety and security due to the visibility of the security guards as these are the two items with the highest mean scores of 4.55 and 4.52, respectively.

Finally, the indicator of empathy obtained a category mean of 4.45, which is described as very high. The item on the *treatment of customers with respect* has the highest mean score of 4.48 (very high).

Table 2. Level of Service Quality

Beach Resort's Service Quality	Mean	SD	Description
A. Reliability			
1. efficiency of the management on reservations	4.45	0.71	Very high
2. readiness of guestrooms/ cottages for occupancy	4.38	0.68	Very high
3. modernity of the facilities	4.32	0.70	Very high
4. timeliness of delivery of services	4.30	0.71	Very high
5. cleanliness and maintenance of washed room/ comfort room	4.37	0.71	Very high
6. variety of water recreational activities	4.31	0.73	Very high
Category Mean	4.35	0.58	Very high
B. Tangibility			
1. accessibility of the location	4.23	0.69	Very high
2. cleanliness and maintenance of the seashore	4.40	0.65	Very high
3. sufficiency of lighting facility	4.38	0.70	Very high
4. The personnel's	4.51	0.62	Very high
a. discipline			
b. grooming	4.51	0.61	Very high
c. courteousness	4.54	0.61	Very high
d. honesty	4.51	0.63	Very high

Category Mean	4.44	0.55	Very high
C. Responsiveness			
1.The personnel's			
a. helpfulness	4.52	0.64	Very high
b. readiness to answer all inquiries of customers	4.52	0.64	Very high
c. knowledgeability	4.48	0.68	Very high
d. quickness to respond to the customers' request	4.48	0.72	Very high
Category Mean	4.50	0.63	Very high
D. Assurance			
1. safety and security	4.55	0.67	Very high
2. visibility of security guards	4.52	0.68	Very high
3. availability of rescue team	4.45	0.75	Very high
4. visibility of first aid facility	4.41	0.79	Very high
Category Mean	4.48	0.67	Very high
E. Empathy			
1. provision of undivided attention to customers	4.43	0.71	Very high
2. readiness to serve customers at any time	4.45	0.68	Very high
3. respectfulness to the customers	4.48	0.66	Very high
4. delivery of customer needs	4.44	0.71	Very high
Category Mean	4.45	0.66	Very high
Overall Mean	4.44	0.55	Very high

The data in Table 3 pertain to the result of the level of customer satisfaction. These are determined by three domains. The level of customer satisfaction is very high, with an overall mean of 4.20. The standard deviation ranges from 0.64 to 0.86, which implies that the responses are homogeneous.

It received a category mean of 4.07, which is considered high in terms of repeat purchase indicator. The item concerning premises safety and sanitation received the greatest rating, with a mean score of 4.14, which is regarded high, while the item about providing fair prices received the lowest rating, with a mean score of 3.94, which is still considered high.

The purchase retention obtained a category mean of 4.34, described as very high. The strength of the resort lies in the provision of spacious, *clean, and safe parking areas* with the highest mean score of 4.37 (very high).

As regards customer loyalty, it obtained a category mean of 4.19 or described as high. The *efficiency of payment processes* had the highest mean score of 4.32 (very high). The availability of a foreign currency exchange facility, on the other hand, had the lowest mean score of 3.89. (high).

Table 3. Level of Customer Satisfaction

Customer Satisfaction	Mean	SD	Description
A. Repeat Purchase			
1. Provision of quality products and services.	4.12	0.76	High
2. Provision of reasonable prices	3.94	0.86	High
3. Safety and sanitation of the premises	4.14	0.73	High
4. Dependability of the menus and services	4.11	0.74	High
5. Uniqueness of the products/services	4.02	0.79	High
Category Mean	4.07	0.69	High
B. Purchase Retention			
1. Expertise, courteousness, and honesty of the personnel.	4.34	0.72	Very high
2. Space, cleanliness, and safety of parking area.	4.37	0.72	Very high
3. Safety, hygiene, and sanitation.	4.36	0.73	Very high
4. Promptness of service	4.34	0.70	Very high
5. Provision of Medical services.	4.31	0.80	Very high
Category Mean	4.34	0.66	Very high
C. Customer Loyalty			

1. Sustainability of customer relationship through the online reservation services	4.27	0.79	Very high
2. Excellence of service	4.26	0.73	Very high
3. Availability of foreign currency exchange facility	3.89	1.01	High
4. Modernization of function rooms	4.21	0.75	Very high
5. Efficiency of payment processes	4.32	0.79	Very high
Category Mean	4.19	0.70	High
Overall Mean	4.20	0.64	Very high

Table 4 shows the result of the variable correlation. Customer satisfaction has a significant moderate relationship with marketing mix ($r=.58, p.05$), according to the statistics. Customer satisfaction, on the other hand, is significantly correlated with service quality ($r=.68, p.05$).

Table 4. Correlation of Variables

Variables paired with Customer Satisfaction	R	p-value	Interpretation
Marketing Mix	.58	.00	Significant
Service Quality	.68	.00	Significant

The outcome of the regression analysis is presented in Table 5. The data revealed that both independent variables—marketing mix and service quality could significantly influence customer satisfaction on its singular capacity ($p<.05$). Between the two variables, service quality has a more significant influence, as manifested by a beta coefficient of .52. Also, this coefficient signifies that for every unit increase in service quality leads to .52 increases in customer service. On the other hand, every unit increase in marketing mix corresponds to .27 increases in customer satisfaction.

As a model, the r^2 of .512 indicates that the combined influence of marketing mix and service quality is significant for 51.2 percent of the variation in customer satisfaction. This means that additional elements that may have a major impact on customer satisfaction, equal to 48.8%, are not covered in this study.

Table 5. Influencers of Customer Satisfaction

Variables	Beta Coefficient	p-value	T	Interpretation
Marketing mix	.27	.00	5.42	Significant
Service quality	.52	.00	10.35	Significant

$r^2 = .512$
 $F = 157.59$
 $p = .00$

IV. DISCUSSION

Marketing Mix Strategy

The result means that the resorts effectively execute and deliver a marketing strategy, and the marketing mix implementation is extensive. It supports the finding of Thieu, Hieu, Huyen, Binh, and Hoang (2017) that the marketing mix is an undeniably important tool for establishments. The use of marketing tools such as the four Ps allows marketers to move further and to provide customer satisfaction.

In terms of product results, the level of marketing mix supports the observation of Pride, Ferrel, &Hult (2014) that product quality means the general features of a product. Products that stand for anticipated quality, given that the notion of quality varies from marketer to customer. Also, with that of Tseng and Hu (2014)who believes that product development in the marketing mix depends on the choice of the customer, which is why businesses fully understand the customer's need to develop the right product for the market thoroughly. Furthermore, it confirms the contention of Hall (2015) that to satisfy the customers, the establishment must determine what customers need or want and then produce the right product with the right quality standard.

In terms of promotion the results confirmed the study of Rugova&Prenaj (2016) that social media is an effective advertising strategy that has contributed to the creation of new company prospects, the development of a stronger market position, or the alteration of customer behavior. In the same manner, the use of platforms like Facebook and Instagram would maintain customer relationships, channels, and thus becoming vital resources and supporting key activities (Gatautis, Vitkauskaite, & de Reuver, 2017).

However, the result for promotion through sponsorship or exchange deal implies that collaboration with sponsors or having exchange deals with other business entities is sometimes extensive. This finding explains the observation of Ingram (2017) that other forms of promotions may not apply to all types of businesses.

When it comes to the place, the result confirms the finding of Payam (2015) that it is essential for the tourist destination to have police in the place to ensure the security of the tourist. Also, tourism police are believed to help create an image of the destination and advertise the place.

While the price result connotes that respondent find recreational activities as moderately expensive, and few customers can afford the rates. This result supports the observation of Stadler (2015) that customers consider price when deciding to buy products and services. The price is the primary factor considered by the customers.

Service Quality

The result of the study implies that the guests always experience service quality components in the five components or dimensions.

The reliability result confirms the findings of Ottawa Chamber of Commerce, (2014) and Ibrahimi, et. al. (2015) quality service includes the ability of service providers to deliver promised services on time, reliably and accurately, how they maintain an error-free record in the establishment, and how they address customer complaints and difficulties.

In the tangibility dimension the finding connotes that the customers always experience the service quality as regards location, cleanliness and maintenance of the resort, the sufficiency of lighting facilities, and the dependability of the personnel. This favorable result on tangibility confirms the idea of Ibrahimi, et. al. (2015) that tidiness and neatness are essential to be in the establishment. Moreover, the result supports the study of Panda and Das (2014) that the tangible service can be experienced without having to pay for it.

Responsiveness results supports the reflection of Nabi (2012) and Berinyuy (2010) that customers are satisfied when the personnel help the customers and address their complaints knowledgeably.

Assurance result is parallel to the observation of Umeze & Ohen (2015) that safety and security are the factors that the customers consider in choosing a place. Also, it confirms the argument of Armstrong et. al. (2014) that safety and security is the primary priority of the customers. Furthermore, the result supports the generalizations that guests feel satisfied when the area is secured and has a first-aid facility (Mellina&Aballe, 2013; Yulisetiari, 2014 & Hinlayagan, 2018).

Lastly, the finding of empathy implies that the resort staff possesses the personality that the customers are expecting from the personnel. They are found to have focus when serving the customers, ready to serve all the time, respectful and responsive to the needs of the customers. This finding confirmed and backed up Bahadur, Zulfiqar, and Aziz (2018)'s claim that empathic employee behavior during service encounters boosts customer satisfaction and loyalty to the company.

Customer Satisfaction

Repeat purchase. This indicates that the resort's products and services, pricing structure, safety and sanitization, and menus are satisfactory to the guests. Hence, given this level of satisfaction, they avail of the services repeatedly. This finding backs up the conclusion of Mandal (2016) that guest satisfaction helps companies maintain excellent partnerships with their guests and renders the assurance of loyalty with the establishment. Also, It confirms Singh and Khan's (2012) conclusion that a business capacity to entice and persist new consumers is influenced not just in terms of its services and products, but also by how it treats existing customers and the reputation it builds inside and across the market.

Purchase retention. This finding fortifies Saber, Ibrahim, Mustapha, Salim, Sandikau, and Lajis (2017) findings that parking convenience is one of the variables influencing customers' decision to buy again and stay with a company. It

also supports the finding of Mandal (2016) and Reinartz and Kumar (2003) that customer retention programs help companies maintain excellent partnerships with their guests and stay to the establishment.

Customer Loyalty. This indicates that the guest-respondents are pleased with the online reservations, service quality, function room modernism, and payment process. Thus, they remain loyal to the resort. This finding supports the generalization of Nam and Carnie (2011) and Hinlayagan (2018) that customers become loyal when they are satisfied and have an intimate and personal connection to the products and services of the business. Moreover, it agrees on the realizations that customer satisfaction of the company's services or output depends to a greater extent on loyalty (Shaikh and Khan, 2011), customer satisfaction of the company's services or output depends to a greater extent on loyalty (Zephan, 2018) and customer satisfaction causes a shift in customer loyalty (Ibuho, 2015).

Correlation of Variables

This finding means that the greater the extent of implementation of the marketing mix would necessarily lead to customer satisfaction. This result confirms the concept of Kotler (2015) that the two significant purposes of marketing, is satisfying the current growing customers and attracting new customers. This finding shows that the greater the quality of the services, the higher the level of customer satisfaction. Also, this finding backs up Kotler and Keller's (2009) claim that service quality is the sum of a service's qualities and characteristics that meet consumers' expectations. It also supports the findings of Agbor (2011), who found a close correlation between service quality and customer satisfaction.

Influencers of Customer Satisfaction

This study confirms Zikmund, Babin, Carr, and Griffin's (2013) claim that customer happiness is a marketing mix that a buyer encounters while purchasing a product or service. Also, it confirms the explanation of Abd Wahab et al. (2016) marketing mix and service quality as essential elements to satisfy customers that could lead to loyalty. Furthermore, it supports Khan, Yusoff, and Kakar (2017) findings that service quality has a favorable and significant impact on customer satisfaction. The happiness of visitors, the desire to buy again, and the growth of businesses are all intimately related to service quality aspects.

V. CONCLUSION

The marketing mix is being implemented extensively on the Island Garden City of Samal selected beach resorts. The promotion has the lowest category mean score of 3.57 among the four indicators, even though it is nevertheless extensive. This conclusion suggests that the beach resort owners understood the value of the marketing mix in their respective businesses. On selected beach resorts in IGACOSor Island Garden City of Samal, the degree of service quality aspects in terms of tangibility, reliability, assurance, responsiveness, and empathy is very high. This indicates that the guests received consistently high-quality service. Customers' satisfaction in the selected beach resorts is indeed high. This indicates that they are really pleased with the resorts' services. Customer satisfaction and marketing mix techniques have a significant relationship. Customer satisfaction is also strongly linked to the level of service provided. Furthermore, customer satisfaction is greatly influenced by marketing mix strategy and service quality (p.05). With a beta coefficient of .52, service quality has a greater impact on customer satisfaction than the marketing mix. The findings supported Somocor's (2017) hypothesis that marketing mix strategy and service quality were substantially connected with customer satisfaction. It also backs up Mustawadjuhaefa et al. (2017)'s claim that the marketing mix and quality service have a big impact on customer satisfaction.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

Since the extent of implementation is only high, this is indicative that the owners may look for more strategies to promote their products and services, not just locally but also internationally. Also, it is suggested to the beach resorts to have an exchange deal with TV networks to promote the establishments comprehensively and efficiently. The owners or managers of the selected beach resorts may sustain the service quality and customer satisfaction through updated training and seminars of the staff, and provision of innovative business processes and recreational water activities. Since some customers find the price to be unreasonable, it is suggested that owners or managers may evaluate the price of the services to assess their reasonability and competitiveness. The management may also consider having a foreign currency exchange facility for foreigners. Other researchers may look into elements other than service quality and marketing mix that have a major impact on consumer satisfaction.. Also, these researchers may consider using a mixed-methods design to draw out information in more depth.

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